
A NOVEL HIGHT TEMPERATURE SINGLE POLYMER COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

In the last few decades, polymeric composites have been used in many fields, such as aerospace, automotive, infrastructure and construction, which could be attributed to their light-weight and excellent mechanical properties. Before single polymer composites (SPCs) were introduced, the polymeric composites had been considered as being composed of fiber reinforcement and polymer matrix which were given by chemically different materials. SPCs are at the odds with the traditional definition of composites, they are composed of the same polymer or of polymers belonging to the same type. Nowadays SPCs have attracted many industrial and commercial interests since they could compete with traditional composites in various applications based on their lighter-weight, favored recycling and beneficial performance. The characteristics of them, especially for the mechanical properties, are depended on the reinforcing component which is higher anisotropic compared to the matrix, which show that the properties of them could be controlled not only by the raw material type but also by the processing method since the properties are determined by the anisotropy of SPCs component. The SPCs based on the chemical composition of polypropylene, polyethylene, polyethylene terephthalate or poly lactic acid were come out. However, few SPCs did work over 220°C as reported. In the present work, a SPC based on polysulfonamide was prepared by the special molding process. The thermal properties were studied by TGA and DMA. And the results indicated that this novel SPC had good thermal properties since its onset decomposition temperature was over 420 °C and the glass transition temperature was over 300 °C.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymeric composites have been used in many fields duo to their light-weight and excellent mechanical properties. And the interest in the composites recycling has increased significantly recently, especially for the material used in the fields of aerospace and automotive [1-2]. Single polymer composite (SPC) was deemed as a promising approach to solve this problem since all these materials were thermal-plastics [3]. Additionally, as

homogeneous composites, SPC was provided good interfacial bonding by the reinforcement and matrix of the same polymer or of polymers belonging to the same type, which would help the material get excellent mechanical properties [4]. Thus, the treasure of SPC was growing, and several kinds of SPC came out since Capiati and Porter had been prepared HDPE based SPC (HDPE_f/HDPE composites) with HDPE fiber in 1927 [5]. Nowadays the formula of SPC have been varied, they could be prepared with not only fiber and powder but also with the combination of fiber, powder, film and textile [6-8]. And some novel SPC were coming out with the development of novel polymer and organic fibers, such as polyethylene terephthalate or poly lactic acid based SPCs [9-14]. However, few SPCs did work over 220°C as reported since the high temperature organic fiber had poor processability, because the plasticizing temperature and decomposition temperature of them were close. In order to developing a novel high performance SPC, one high temperature organic fiber named polysulfonamide(PSA) fiber was successfully plasticized by the special molding process, and a novel high temperature single polymer composite named PSA_f/PSA composite was prepared. In the present work, the thermal properties of this material were studied in detail by Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) and Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Polysulfonamide fiber (PSA_f) was supplied from Shanghai Tanlon Fiber Co., Ltd., and the chemical structure of polysulfonamide was shown as scheme 1. Besides, the parameters of the fiber were listed in Table 1.

Scheme 1. The chemical structure of polysulfonamide

Items	Values
Density [g/cm ³]	1.42
Tensile Strength [cN/dtex]	≥3.0
Elongation [%]	20~25
Soft Temperature [°C]	367
Onset Temperature [°C]	422

Table 1. Parameters of PSA fiber

2.2 Preparation of PSAf/PSA

The fibers were cut into 3mm, and then they were preprocessed with acetone and water in order to getting rid of the oiling agent. The preprocessed short PSA fibers were heated to 200 °C to remove moisture. Subsequently, the fibers were plasticized by the special molding process as reported [15].

2.3 Characterization

Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed with a TA Q500 from 80 to 750°C at

a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere, and the thermal stable residue was formed. About 10mg of a sample was put into a ceramic cell and placed on a detector plate. Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA) was characterized with a TA Q800 in the air. The specimen of 60×10×3 mm was loaded in a three-point bending mode from 50 to 300°C at a heating rate of 5 °C /min with a frequency of 1 Hz.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal stability of PSA_f/PSA

The thermal stability of the cured epoxy resins were studied with thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA). Figure 1 showed the TGA curves of PSA_f/PSA composite at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. And values of the onset decomposition temperature (T_{onset}), 5% weight loss decomposition temperature ($T_{5\%}$), 30% weight loss decomposition temperature ($T_{30\%}$) and the char yield at 750°C were listed in Table 2.

Figure 1: TGA curves of PSA_f/PSA at a heating rate of 10 °C/min

To further investigate the thermal stability of the composites, the heat resistance index was calculated by a statistical method as equation (1) [16].

$$T_c = 0.49[T_1 + 0.6(T_2 - T_1)] \quad (1)$$

where T_c is the value of the heat resistance index, T_1 and T_2 are the 5% and 30% weight loss temperature. The results were listed in Table 2.

System	T_{onset} (°C)	$T_{5\%}$ (°C)	$T_{30\%}$ (°C)	T_c (°C)	Char yield (%, @750°C)
PSA-SPC	424	433	535	242	54.3

Table 2: The thermal stability parameters of PSA_f/PSA

All the results indicated that PSA_f/PSA composite exhibited a reasonable thermal

stability since the decomposition temperature of PSA_f/PSA composite was up to 420°C, and its char yield at 750°C was over 50% in nitrogen atmosphere. Besides, the results of the heat resistance index (T_c) suggested that PSA_f/PSA composite was able to be used under 240°C sequentially. All of these can be attributed to the unique aromatic backbone structure.

3.2 Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis of PSA_f/PSA

More detailed information was obtained from the measurements of the dynamic mechanical behavior of PSA_f/PSA composite, as Figure 2 shown. As quantified mechanical performance at elevated temperatures, storage modulus (E') was seemed as an important indicator of the performance of polymer composites. The storage modulus curves displayed significant drops in the temperature range of 300-310°C. In addition, as the indicator of cross-linking density, the glass transition temperature (T_g) of this material was obtained with three methods, being determined with the inflection point of storage modulus curves, the peak temperature of loss modulus curves and $\tan\delta$ curves, and the results were showed in Table 3, which indicated that the glass transition temperature (T_g) of PSA_f/PSA composite was over 300°C.

Above all, PSA_f/PSA composite kept excellent thermal property from PSA fiber, and it could be used under 240°C sequentially and 300°C for a short time in theory.

Figure 2. DMA curves of PSA_f/PSA at a heating rate of 5 °C/min with a frequency of 1 Hz.

System	The glass transition temperature (T_g , °C)		
	E'	E''	Tan δ
PSA-SPC	309	322	340

Table 3. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of PSA_f/PSA determined with three methods

4 CONCLUSIONS

A novel high performance SPC named PSA_f/PSA composite was prepared from polysulfonamide (PSA) fiber with the special molding process. The thermal properties of this material were studied in the present work. Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) results indicated that PSA_f/PSA composite exhibited a reasonable thermal stability since the decomposition temperature of PSA_f/PSA composite was up to 420°C, its char yield at 750°C

was over 50% in nitrogen atmosphere, and the heat resistance index (T_c) was over 240°C. Besides, Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA) verified that PSA_f/PSA composite had excellent thermal mechanical behavior since the glass transition temperature (T_g) of PSA_f/PSA composite was over 300°C. In general, all the results showed that PSA_f/PSA composite kept excellent thermal property from PSA fiber, and it could be used under 240°C sequentially and 300°C for a short time in theory.

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